

Community-Based Strategies for Diarrheal Disease Management and Prevention in Children Below Five Years.

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Abstract

Diarrheal diseases are a major public health problem associated with high morbidity and mortality in children below the ages of five. Globally, it accounts for 9% of deaths among children less than 5 years. In spite of a reduction in the mortality by 34.3% in Children below five years between 2005 and 2015 and 20.8% among people of all ages, its prevalence remains high above the expected in sub-Saharan Africa including Cameroon. This review aimed at identifying the different strategies used by mothers and caregivers of children under five at the community level in the management and prevention of diarrheal diseases. Most of the strategies reported in the literature used by mothers and caregivers for the management and prevention of diarrheal in children at the community level included rehydration with oral rehydration solution, zinc supplementation, use of nutrient rich foods, access to safe drinking water, use of improved sanitation services, hand washing, exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months of life, good personal and food hygiene, health education about infection spread, handling and storage of food and the control of carrier pathogens such as houseflies and Rotavirus vaccination being the most effective. Vaccination against the Rota virus is the most effective prevention and management strategy against diarrheal on children below 5 at the community level. There is need for more sensitization on the importance of vaccination against the Rota virus in communities especially vulnerable communities with poor access to safe drinking water in order to curb the impact of diarrheal diseases in children at the community level.

Key words: Diarrhoea Disease, Management and prevention, children under five.

Introduction

Diarrhoea disease is a major public health problem worldwide with an estimated 525,000 children under the age of five dying annually due to diarrhea. It is the second-leading cause of death among under-five children. In Africa about 94% of the burden of diarrhoeal disease is attributed to the environment comprising of elements such as unsafe drinking water and poor sanitation [1]. However, most diarrhoea diseases in these children can be managed and prevented using appropriate measures and remedies such as ORS administration and anti-biotherapy in some cases with overall environmental hygiene and sanitation prevention practices such as improvement in water quality, proper waste handling and disposal, improved domestic and personal hygiene like handwashing, proper waste disposal, good practices in preparation, handling and storage of food, appropriate child feeding practices, control of carrier pathogens such as houseflies that transmit diarrhoea and immunization [2,3]. Evidence has demonstrated that, Rota virus vaccine is effective in reducing diarrhoea mortality in children below five. However, the Rotavirus vaccines have the highest efficacy against severe rotavirus disease and in 2014, the government of Cameroon included the vaccine into the routine vaccination calendar and it is administered orally between 6 to 12 weeks and 10 to 14 weeks in order to reduce infant morbidity from diarrhoeal diseases [4]. The World Health Organization defines diarrhoea as the passage of three or more loose or liquid stools per day (or more frequent passage than is normal for the individual [5]. Acute diarrhoea which is the passage of stools with abnormal consistency and frequency in a day (e.g. more than three times) which lasts for less than two weeks, is a syndrome that is frequently not subject to differential diagnosis in medical practice [6]. Bacterial diarrhoeal cases are the most prevalent of all diarrhoeal cases around the globe [7]. Commonly reported enteric bacterial diarrhoeal diseases and the causative agents are botulism (*Clostridium botulinum*), *Campylobacter gastroenteritis* (*Campylobacter jejuni*), cholera (*Vibrio cholerae*), *Escherichia coli gastroenteritis*, Salmonellosis (various *Salmonella serovars*), Shigellosis (*Shigella spp.*), and Staphylococcal food poisoning (*Staphylococcus aureus enterotoxins*) [8]. Children below five years of age have the most at risk from foodborne pathogens, including Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* O157, *Campylobacter*, *Shigella*, *Yersinia*, *Salmonella*, and *Cryptosporidium* [9]. In the past few decades, the awareness in handwashing has tremendously reduced the burden of diarrhoea caused by enteric bacteria and protozoans, yet, it has less impact on diarrhoea caused by viruses [10].

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Diarrhoeal diseases emerge in most developing countries as a major cause of sickness and death in young children [11]. Evidence has shown that, diarrhoeal diseases cause nearly 5 million deaths annually in under five children in developing countries. It was the cause of every tenth child's death in 2017-more than half a million children that died in 2017 died from diarrhoeal diseases [12]. Diarrhoeal disease mortality can be effectively reduced at reasonable cost by oral rehydration, zinc supplementation, use of selected antibiotics and continuous feeding.[13] and possibly other measures. diarrhoeal diseases disproportionately affect locations with poor access to health care, safe water, and sanitation, and low-income or marginalized populations. These observations illustrate that although challenges exist, diarrhoea mortality is largely avoidable and renewed efforts to reduce disease burden are urgently needed.

Diarrhoea is one of the commonest illnesses that has the greatest negative impact on the growth and development of infants and young children[14]. Apart from diarrhoea being a major cause of morbidity and mortality, it also has a significant impact on growth due to reduction in appetite, altered feeding practices and decreased absorption of nutrients[15]. There is a marked negative relationship between diarrhoea and physical growth and development of a child. Each day of illness due to diarrhoea produces a weight deficit of 20 g – 40 g. Infants who spend more than 20% of their time with diarrhoea have a weight deficit of approximately 370 g at follow-up after one year of age [16].

Diarrhoea in under-fives in sub-Saharan Africa including Cameroon is associated with catastrophic expenditures for most households given more than 80% of the population live below the poverty line. In addition, it is a burden to the fragile health system which is already overburdened with other communicable diseases such as malaria which is endemic in the region. In Cameroon, there is limited data on the best strategies for the management and prevention of diarrhoea at the community level in children below the age of five. In Cameroon, the community-based prevalence of what? ranges from 16% to 23% among under-fives. [17,18]. Moreover, 15% of deaths among children under 5 years of age are attributable to diarrheal diseases [17]. Cameroon adopted the integrated disease surveillance and response (IDSR) strategy in 2005 [18]. The IDSR strategy is used for the surveillance of diarrheal diseases in Cameroon.

This review therefore aimed at identifying the best different strategies that can be used by mothers and caregivers of children under five at the community level in the management and prevention of to manage and prevent diarrhoeal diseases.

Methods

Studies reporting the community management of diarrhoeal diseases were identified from a search of databases including PubMed, PubMed Central, and Google scholar for articles published from 2015 and 2022. The search was not restricted to publications in the English Language, only to studies that had abstracts in English. The key subject terms included one or combinations of the following: Home management of diarrhoeal diseases AND children, diarrhea (or diarrhoea) and prevention, Diarrhoeal control OR diarrhoea prevention.

Other articles were identified by using the PubMed option of related articles and checked the reference lists of the original and review articles.

Results:

1. Management strategies for diarrhoea diseases in under five children

Integrated Management of Childhood Illness

Home management of diarrhoea has been recognized and advocated for by WHO, United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) and Integrated Management of Childhood Illness to reduce the impact of diarrhoea, especially in children. Evidence has proven that, oral rehydration delivered within primary health care programs is an effective and relatively inexpensive intervention for the reduction of mortality due to dehydrating diarrheas [19]. Other interventions are also required, for three main reasons; first, like all health services delivered at the community level, oral rehydration programmes face operational constraints that may militate against the achievement of their full potential impact. Secondly, oral rehydration is of limited use in the treatment of chronic or dysenteric diarrhoeas and, in areas of the world where there is considerable proportion of diarrhoeal disease mortality, the effect of oral rehydration programmes on the overall mortality from diarrhoeal diseases may be modest. Thirdly, oral rehydration can be expected to have little or no impact on diarrhoea morbidity rates. A multifaceted strategy is therefore preferable, in which oral rehydration is one of several anti-diarrhoea measures being implemented simultaneously, with mutually reinforcing and complementary impacts.

The Diarrhoeal Diseases Control (CDD) Program of the World Health Organization

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The Diarrhoeal Diseases Control (CDD) Program of the World Health Organization has, since its inception in 1978, advocated the following four-part strategy for diarrhoea control:

- Improved case management, with particular emphasis on the early use of oral rehydration therapy in acute diarrhoea and on appropriate feeding during illness and convalescence;
- Improved maternal and child health care, with particular emphasis on breast-feeding, weaning practices, personal and domestic hygiene, and maternal nutrition;
- Improved use and maintenance of drinking water and sanitation facilities, and
- Improved food hygiene; - detection and control of epidemics.

In the first years of the CDD programme, greatest emphasis was placed upon oral rehydration as the primary intervention for reducing diarrhoeal disease mortality among young children [19]. The CDD programme has developed detailed recommendations for oral rehydration therapy [20] and the production of oral rehydration salts, [21] and has worked with governments of Member countries in the planning, implementation and evaluation of oral rehydration and other diarrhoea control measures [22]. With the implementation of CDD programmes in over 35 countries, it is now appropriate to supplement the emphasis on oral rehydration by developing, in detail, other interventions for diarrhoea control and undertaking the necessary field research and evaluation to establish their feasibility and cost-effectiveness [23].

Table 1. Interventions for reducing diarrhoeal morbidity or mortality among children under five years of age

Strategy	Intervention action
Case management	
Oral rehydration therapy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administration of oral rehydration solution in the home. • Administration of oral rehydration solution at a medical facility.
Non-oral rehydration therapy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administration of rehydration by intravenous or other routes at a medical facility.
Appropriate feeding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting the appropriate feeding of children during diarrhoeal illness and convalescence.
Chemotherapy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administration of therapeutic agents at home. • Administration of therapeutic agents at a medical facility.
Increasing host resistance to infection and/or illness and/ or death	
Maternal nutrition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving prenatal nutrition to reduce the incidence of low birth-weight. • Improving prenatal and postnatal nutrition to improve the quality of breast milk.
Child nutrition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting exclusive breast-feeding up to age 4-6 months and partial breast-feeding thereafter. • Improving weaning practices for children aged 4-18 months (introducing non-milk foods not later than the sixth month, continuing breast-feeding for as long as possible and using nutritious and locally available weaning foods). • Supplementary feeding to improve the nutritional status of children aged 6-59 months.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting the use of growth charts by mothers as an aid to proper child nutrition and childcare.
Immunization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rotavirus and/or cholera immunization (when effective and tested vaccines are available) of the child and/or mother. Measles immunization to reduce measles-associated diarrhoea.
Chemoprophylaxis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemoprophylaxis of children at special risk, such as contacts of known cases, to reduce the incidence and/or severity of diarrhoea.
Reducing transmission of the pathogenic agents of diarrhoeal diseases	
Water supply and excreta disposal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Constructing water supplies that improve the quality and availability of water for domestic purposes, and improve excreta disposal facilities; and providing the necessary educational support to ensure the use and maintenance of these new facilities.
Personal and domestic hygiene	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting specific features of personal and domestic hygiene, such as hand washing by appropriate educational campaigns.
Food hygiene	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting improved practices for the preparation and storage of foods, both commercially and in the home, and especially emphasizing the hygienic preparation of weaning foods.
Control of zoonotic reservoirs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Control of infection of domestic and farm animals by pathogens causing diarrhoea in man.
Fly control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Control of flies, especially flies breeding in association with human or animal faeces.
Controlling and/or preventing diarrhoea epidemics	

Epidemic surveillance, investigation and control	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Improving the ability to identify and investigate an epidemic early in its course and the capacity to implement effective control activities.
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Feachem *et al.*, [24]

Treatment of diarrhoea with ORS is a simple, proven, high-impact intervention that can be provided in-home settings by caretakers or by health care providers at community and facility levels to prevent dehydration due to diarrhoea and decrease related deaths. There is evidence that ORS may reduce diarrhoea specific mortality by up to 93 % [25]. However, data analysis from recent population-based household surveys show that population coverage for this basic but effective intervention is still very low, particularly in countries that are hardest hit by diarrheal diseases. In sub-Saharan Africa, only about one in 3 children experiencing diarrheal episodes receives ORS, and the proportion receiving zinc is below 5 % [26].

Although appropriate treatment of diarrhoea is simple and can be done at home, seeking care from appropriate providers outside the home is also recommended because harmful practices based on beliefs and misconceptions are prevalent, especially in low-income countries where the diarrhoea mortality is high. A systematic review of harmful practices in childhood diarrhoea management found high and variable levels of harmful practices [27], such restriction of food and fluids, including breastfeeding. A recent analysis by Perin *et al.* (28) in 2015 in six African countries found a high prevalence of fluid curtailment during episodes of diarrhoea. The authors also reported that there was also an association between seeking care outside of the home and higher rates of fluid curtailment, particularly for care seeking from non-government health providers.

2.0. Prevention and control strategies

Strategies for controlling diarrheal diseases have remained substantially unchanged for decades. The World Health Organization [29] re-evaluated these interventions to determine the extent to which they have been effectively implemented and their effect.

Promotion of Exclusive Breastfeeding

Studies have shown that exclusive breastfeeding protects very young infants from diarrheal disease in two ways: first, breast milk contains both immune (specific) and nonimmune (nonspecific) antimicrobial factors; second, exclusive breastfeeding eliminates the intake of potentially contaminated food and water. Breast milk also provides all the nutrients most infants need up to age 6 months. For instance, a community based study carried out in... (any country) found that exclusive breast feeding When exclusive breastfeeding is continued during diarrhoea, it also diminishes the adverse impact on nutritional status. The optimal duration of exclusive

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breastfeeding is six months [30]. A meta-analysis of three observational studies in developing countries shows that breastfed children under age 6 months are 6.1 times less likely to die of diarrhoea than infants who are not breastfed [31].

This underpins the global campaign to promote exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months of life by increasing both the initiation and the duration of exclusive breastfeeding. The strategies include the following:

- Hospital policies and actions to encourage breastfeeding and discourage bottle-feeding.
- Counselling and education provided by peers or health workers
- Mass media and community education
- Mothers' support groups.

Improved Complementary Feeding Practices

Ideally, complementary foods should be introduced at age 6 months, and breastfeeding should continue for up to two years or even longer to increase birth intervals [32]. Malnutrition is an independent risk predictor for the frequency and severity of diarrheal illness. There is a vicious cycle in which sequential diarrheal disease leads to increasing nutritional deterioration, impaired immune function, and greater susceptibility to infection. The cycle may be broken by interventions to decrease infection incidence to reduce malnutrition [33] or improving nutritional status to reduce the burden of infection [34].

Improved feeding practices to prevent or treat malnutrition could save as many as 800,000 lives per year [35]. Paediatricians have long been aware of an increase in diarrhoea incidence during weaning from exclusive breast milk feeding. Microbial contamination of complementary foods [36] and nutritionally inadequate diets during and after diarrhoea episodes [37] increase the risk.

Rotavirus Immunization

Almost all infants acquire rotavirus diarrhoea early in life, and rotavirus accounts for at least one-third of severe and potentially fatal watery diarrhoea episodes—primarily in developing countries, where an estimated 440,000 vaccine-preventable rotavirus deaths per year occur [38], compared with about a dozen in a developed country such as France [39]. An effective rotavirus vaccine would have a major effect on diarrhoea mortality in developing countries.

Cholera Immunization

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Endemic cholera is primarily a paediatric disease, although adult morbidity and mortality are significant, especially during epidemics. The lethality of cholera is due to the physiological consequences of rapid and profound dehydration. Oral rehydration therapy has dramatically improved survival and reduced the cost of treatment. Wherever parenteral and oral rehydration is readily available, even in epidemic situations, a cholera mortality rate above 1 percent indicates failure of the public health system to provide appropriate case management. A vaccine would further reduce the morbidity and mortality associated with cholera in endemic areas; however, developing an effective, safe vaccine has proven difficult. The most immunogenic and protective vaccines tested thus far are administered orally. Two such vaccines were licensed: an attenuated live vaccine and a heat-killed vaccine combined with recombinant cholera toxin B subunit, which functions as an immunoadjuvant [40].

Measles Immunization

Measles is known to predispose children to diarrheal diseases secondary to measles-induced immunodeficiency. Feachem and Koblinsky in [1984] [39] estimated that measles vaccine given to 45% to 90% of infants would prevent 44% to 64% of measles cases, 0.6% to 3.8% of diarrheal episodes, and 6% to 26% of diarrheal deaths among children under five respectively. Global measles immunization coverage is now approaching 80%, and the disease has been eliminated from the Americas, raising hopes for global elimination in the near future [40], with a predictable reduction in diarrhoea as well.

Improved water and sanitary Facilities and Promotion of Personal and Domestic Hygiene

Human faeces are the primary source of diarrheal pathogens. Poor sanitation, lack of access to clean water, and inadequate personal hygiene are responsible for an estimated 90% of childhood diarrhoea [41]. Promotion of hand washing reduces diarrhoea incidence by an average of 33 percent [42]; it works best when it is part of a package of behavior change interventions.

Conclusion

Childhood diarrhoea disease still poses a significant health problem within the community, as it is a major cause of malnutrition, in children below five years of age. However, interventions such as, rehydration with ORS, zinc supplementation, use of nutrient rich foods, access to safe drinking

water, use of improved sanitation services, handwashing, exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months of life, good personal and food hygiene, health education about infection spread and rotavirus vaccination are strategies which if well implemented, will curb the burden of the disease in children below five years in the community.

Recommendation

There is therefore need for improved formula for ORS solution with reduced levels of glucose and salt should be developed, which shortens the duration of diarrhoea and the need for unscheduled intravenous fluids [43]-this should be in line with the administration of zinc supplements in order to reduce the duration and severity of the episode [44]. In addition, dehydration should be prevented through the early administration of increased amounts of appropriate fluids available in the home, and ORS solution. Also, adequate dietary management during and after diarrheal disease should be encouraged to allow catch-up growth and a return to good nutritional condition during convalescence. Furthermore, capacity building in implementing preventive interventions such as sanitation, water source improvements, household water storage and safe storage, rotavirus immunization and training of community health workers for early identification and detection of cases for prompt referral should be highly encouraged.

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